

ROLE OF ULTRASOUND FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF ENDOMETRIAL HYPERPLASIA

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Summary. Endometrial hyperplasia is a common condition due to exposure to exogenous or endogenous estrogens along with relative progesterone deficiency. It is a precursor to endometrial cancer, which is one of the most common gynecological malignancies. To avoid the development of endometrial carcinoma, it is important that the clinician closely monitor the signs and symptoms of endometrial hyperplasia. Ultrasound examination (ultrasound) of the pelvic organs (without bleeding) is of great informative value for the prediction and early diagnosis of endometrial hyperplasia, especially its pathological forms, and is the main prognostic marker. This article discusses the role of ultrasound in the diagnosis and treatment of endometrial hyperplasia.

Relevance. In most countries of the world, there is an increase in the incidence of endometrial cancer. According to the statistics of our Republic of Uzbekistan, over the past 5 years, this pathology has increased by 28.7% [14,15]. It is known that the development of endometrioid adenocarcinoma is associated with endometrial hyperplasia, especially its recurrent forms, however, data on its prevalence are extremely scarce, since there is no official registration of this insidious pathology, although the assessment of the occurrence of GE (endometrial hyperplasia) plays an important role not only in the aspect of management tactics associated with uterine bleeding in women in the perimenopausal period, but also to prevent the development of endometrial cancer [13,16]. Proliferative processes in the endometrium are considered as a precancerous condition with varying degrees of probability of malignancy [1,4,6,10].

The frequency of malignancy for HE without atypia is up to 1-3%, while for women with atypical hyperplasia and endothelial intraepithelial neoplasia, it is more than 30% (SobczukK 2017., Selen S. et.al. 2020). Such a close relationship and a steady increase in the incidence of HE and

endometrial cancer dictates to specialists and scientists the need to search for effective markers for preclinical diagnosis and prediction of this formidable pathology in patients of late reproductive age [2,3,8,9].

Screening methods for diagnosing HE are transvaginal ultrasound, with an ambiguous echographic picture, it is possible to perform HSG, less often aspirate from the uterine cavity. Methods of reliable diagnosis can be hysteroscopy and separate diagnostic curettage of the uterine mucosa [5,7,11,12].

The purpose of the study: to study the significance of ultrasound studies for the early diagnosis of pathological proliferative processes of the endometrium.

Materials and research methods. Transvaginal ultrasound - scanning is a highly informative, non-invasive, safe method for diagnosing endometrial hyperplastic processes. This method is performed in order to determine the pathology of the endometrium on the 5th-7th day of the menstrual cycle in women of perimenopausal age; normally, the M-echo should not exceed 5-7 mm. With an M-echo value of less than 7 mm, the probability of the presence of HE is extremely low. In order to determine the role of ultrasound of the pelvic organs in the diagnosis of HGE, we conducted a study in 70 women of perimenopausal age 45-55 years old, the average age of patients was 39.4±6.3 years, who had clinical manifestations of pathological proliferation of the endometrium, admitted for inpatient treatment in gynecological departments. The control group consisted of 30 women of reproductive age, who were examined during the proliferative phase of the menstrual cycle (5-7 days). All women were examined according to the general scheme: collection of anamnestic data, examination, assessment of risk factors, ultrasound examination of the small pelvis using transabdominal and transvaginal sensors. Echography and color Doppler examination were carried out using the VOLUSEN 6 device, in two and three-dimensional modes with the creation of a single photobase for each patient for subsequent interpretation of the results, the echographic state of the endometrium was assessed by the most significant M-echo parameters: thickness and structure.

In order to study the features of blood flow, color Doppler was performed, with the help of which the presence of blood flow, localization and number of color loci were visually assessed. The resistance index (IR) of the spiral arteries was measured. Statistical analysis of the results was performed using Student's t-test, Fisher's exact method, χ^2 (Pearson),

correlation analysis was performed using the Stat Graf software package and Microsoft excel.

Survey results and discussion. The analysis of the data obtained was carried out taking into account the thickness of the M-ECHO of the endometrium; in patients of the control group, the value of the M-ECHO varied from 5 to 8 mm and averaged 6.21 ± 0.6 mm. The structure of the endometrium was homogeneous, the "endometrium-myometrium" border was clearly visualized.

The analysis of the echographic picture of the endometrium in patients of perimenopausal age showed that the ultrasound picture of endometrial hyperplasia was characterized by pronounced polymorphism. However, heterogeneity of the structure of the endometrium and the presence of polypoid growths in the uterine cavity were more common than other variants in 45% of patients in the study group. On ultrasound, the endometrium had a diffusely heterogeneous echo structure, which was manifested by the presence of echo-positive and echo-negative inclusions. The absence of a line of closure of the uterine mucosa; uneven outer contour of the M-echo and its performance averaged 9.32 ± 1.12 mm in addition. Patients of perimenopausal age were characterized by a discrepancy in the echogenicity of the endometrium in the phase of the menstrual cycle, and for patients in postmenopause, a decrease in echogenicity.

The use of Doppler ultrasound techniques is important for assessing the condition of the endometrium. when performing color Doppler mapping, the main uterine arteries were recorded in all patients. in the endometrium of patients with endometrial hyperplasia in 50% (n=35) of cases, blood flow was recorded in the spiral arteries, which were not visualized in patients without pathology of the uterine mucosa in the M-echo projection. It should be noted. That the visualization of blood flow in the spiral arteries in patients with endometrial hyperplasia increased when performing ultrasound in the second phase of the menstrual cycle. The resistance index was 0.53 ± 0.03 . The hallmarks of pathological endometrial hyperplasia were the presence of hypervascularization of the subendometrial zone in the affected area and increased blood flow. IR ranged from 0.43 to 0.5 and averaged 0.46 ± 0.04 . The data is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Doppler parameters of the study group.

It should be noted that 10 patients from this study group were postmenopausal. Taking into account the fact that intraendometrial blood flow is not visualized normally in postmenopausal women with Doppler examination, it can be assumed that the vascularization of the endometrial polyp in postmenopausal women is a diagnostic criterion for endometrial hyperplasia with atypia.

Conclusions. Thus, ultrasound diagnostics determines the presence of changes in the endometrium with certain parameters, visualization of blood flow in the spiral arteries can be attributed to early markers predicting the development of proliferative processes and the formation of pathological endometrial hyperplasia, which undoubtedly require further more in-depth examination and, based on the data obtained, the choice of tactics management and treatment of patients in perimenopausal age.

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